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A Realist View of India–China Border Dispute

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Global border disputes remain one of the problematic legacies of colonialism. While regions like Africa and South America did apply the *Uti possidetis juris* principle in the past to prevent disputes that could have erupted from the likelihood of redrawing the borders of newly independent states, India and China have embraced violent confrontations on different occasions over the border between them.

India and China share the longest disputed border in the world.¹ In other words, the border which can be grouped into three different sectors –the Eastern, Central and Western– has become the major source of deadly confrontations or stand-offs between India and China in the last 58 years. Until the hand-to-hand combat of June 15, 2020, that led to the death of 20 Indian soldiers including the injury of another 76 in the Galwan Valley, India and China have been able to manage peace in the Line of Actual Control. The last time the two countries recorded fatality from clashing was in 1975. And when both countries agreed in 1996 not to use explosives and guns near the border –in order to build trust and avoid a confrontation that could escalate–, it appeared that they had finally found the formula to sustain peace.

Unfortunately, the harsh reality of the international system would not allow China and India to build on the agreement of 1996. Instead, it reduced it (the agreement) to what can best be described as another *Pax Romana*. Against this background, this essay seeks to apply the realist theory of international relations to analyse the border dispute between India and China, the two most populous countries in the world.

Evolution of the Dispute

The India-China border dispute can be traced back to the Simla Convention of 1914, where both the representatives of British India and Tibet defined the boundary between the two countries. The representatives of both countries agreed to a *de facto* eastern border known as the McMahon Line.² Unfortunately, China refused to agree and has never agreed with the outcome of the convention, even when the Indian government adopted the boundary as the effective border in the area between India and China.³

1 “Mapping India and China’s Disputed Borders”, Al-Jazeera, accessed December 8, 2020, <https://interactive.aljazeera.com/aje/2020/mapping-india-and-china-disputed-borders/index.html>

2 “The China-India Border Dispute: Its Origins and Impact”, South China Morning Post, accessed December 8, 2020, <https://www.scmp.com/news/china/diplomacy/article/3094884/china-india-border-dispute-its-origins-and-impact>

3 South China Morning Post, “The China-India Border Dispute.”

Eventually, in 1962, the disagreement escalated into a territorial dispute –Sino-Indian War as it is sometimes tagged. The war which lasted for four weeks saw the defeat of India and allowed China to grab extra territory beyond the McMahon Line. Despite this, the two countries found it difficult to agree on an official border, which was why a series of clashes and stand-offs–like the Nathu La clashes of 1967, Tulung La ambush of 1975 and Doklam stand-off–have followed, between when the 1962 war ended and the last fatal fistfight.

In as much as the leaders of India and China will not sit down to agree on an official border or act as rational actors by making some compromises; in as much as Delhi and Beijing will continue to hold on to their maximalist positions, the dispute will never end. And there is every possibility that in the future, China may try to forcefully push further into Arunachal Pradesh—a territory it lays claim to and that appears as Southern Tibet on its map—through another war, given its aggressive penchant for territory. If anyone thinks the prediction is premature or short-sighted, India already lost control over about 300 square kilometres of land along the disputed mountainous terrain in the summer fistfight of 2020.⁴ Based on that outcome, a bold prediction is not out of place.

ANALYSIS

Undoubtedly, all three theoretical perspectives of international relations are applicable to the India-China border dispute. However, because of the trajectory of the essay, realism has been adopted as the instrument of analysis.

Generally, realism presumes that since the international system has no central power to govern it, there is no collective interest, states only prioritize and act according to their self-interest. And in order to survive in the anarchic system, states must amass power.⁵ In other words, realism encourages states to make self-preservation their foremost interest.⁶ And to achieve this, realism warns states against acting morally, as it is capable of undermining their ability to protect themselves.⁷

Fundamentally, the realist theoretical perspective (though brutally honest) has clearly shown that the absence of a central body to enforce rules or the “lawless” nature of the international system naturally pushes states to act badly, use military might and fight wars. In the context of the India–China border dispute, one can argue that both countries had been

4 “India Loses 300 Square km to China after the Bloody Summer in Himalayas, Officials Say,” South China Morning Post, accessed December 8, 2020, <https://amp.scmp.com/news/asia/south-asia/article/3108051/india-loses-300-square-km-china-after-bloody-summer-himalayas>

5 “Understanding Sino-India Relations – A Theoretical Perspective,” The Centre for International Maritime Security, accessed December 8, 2020, <http://cimsec.org/understanding-sino-indian-relations-theoretical-perspective/24896>

6 “Key Theories of International Relations,” Norwich University Online, accessed December 8, 2020, <https://online.norwich.edu/academic-programs/resources/key-theories-of-international-relations>

7 “Theories of International Relations (summary),” SparkNotes, accessed December 8, 2020, <https://www.sparknotes.com/us-government-and-politics/political-science/international-politics/section2/>

driven to war or confrontations as the case may be, on several occasions, because of the inherent urge to protect their interests. Put differently, both India and China are selfish –they do not care about each other or any collective interest. Their national interests determine the way they think, behave and relate with each other. Hence, they will do anything to promote and protect their interests or enforce their foreign policies, even if it means that they have to go to war.

India and China are like every typical state who seeks self-preservation by all means. Therefore, losing control over any part of their territory will be perceived as a threat to self-preservation. Naturally, humans, regardless of their moral standing, react aggressively to whatever threatens to harm them or take their lives. No one wants to die cheaply, especially when they have the means to defend themselves, or no one wants to be vulnerable to a dangerous and preying neighbour. They will do everything within their capability to assert themselves and, if need be, defend their territorial integrity.

Self-preservation is an instinctive behaviour and man is inherently wired this way. Even wild animals or generally, all animals exhibit this trait. This explains why India and China will continue to flex military muscles along the Line of Actual Control. It is all about self-preservation and “the protection of self-interest” –often masks as national interest and implemented as foreign policy. India’s behaviour will always mirror China’s and vice versa. It is just the nature of the international system unless there is a supranational entity [provided states agree to submit to it] to check the lawlessness.

China appears to be aggressively seeking to extend its spheres of influence in Asia. It is riding on the absence of central authority at the international system to enforce law. Given this dire circumstance, India will not act morally. Because acting morally will cost India some parts of its territory and probably create a situation where Delhi would need to take instruction from Beijing before it does anything (Slippery slope effect). India will avoid this looming anti-Westphalian embarrassment, by defending its territorial integrity with measures it deems necessary. And may even seek the support of the United Nations for a peaceful settlement.

Conclusion

The international system is anarchical. Might is always right, and injustice pays. Collective interest is a charade. States are only there to promote and protect their interests. The system exemplifies the Darwinian theory of survival of the fittest. “Fight or die”, “thrive or perish”. This is what has informed the why behind states’ continuous accumulation of power. To an extent, this has brought some balance in the sense that it is very difficult for a big power to bully any state because it may trigger the reaction of the alliance that is committed to protecting the to-be-bullied state. In light of this, state actors (leaders) must explore negotiation exhaustively until a peaceful settlement is achieved. War is not good for any state. Express differently, India and China must resolve the border dispute peacefully, once and for all, even if the price to pay is compromise.

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